

**Buyers' Preference For Honda And Bajaj Two-Wheelers- A
Comparative Study With Special Reference To Palayamkottai,
Tirunelveli District**

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ABSTRACT

India has the largest number of two wheelers in the world with 41.6 million vehicles. India has a mix of 30 percent automobiles and 70 percent two wheelers in the country. India is the second largest two wheeler manufacture in the world. Two wheelers are playing a vital role in the marketing as well as GDP of India. This study focusing on a comparative study on the manufacturing marketing and buyers preference aspects between Honda and Bajaj two wheelers in Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli District of Tamil Nadu.

Keywords: Buyers Preference, Honda and Bajaj Company, Two- Wheeler Industry

INTRODUCTION

Two wheelers market in India is the biggest contributor to the automobile industry with size RS 100000 million. Two wheeler markets in India comprises of three types of two wheelers motorcycle, scooter and mopeds. Foreign collaboration has been playing a major role in the growth of the Indian two wheelers market, and most of them are Japanese firms. The modern two wheelers firms in India have been manufacturing new categories of two wheelers such as step thrush and scooters. These have been produced by combining two are more two wheeler segment. Foreign firms have already taken initiative to own their two wheeler subsidiaries in India.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Two wheeler industries are growing with very fast speed. Every day the new models of two wheelers are introduced in the market. Bajaj and Honda are the major players of two wheeler industries. There is very hard competition between Bajaj and Honda. So to know the

position of the companies, it is necessary to know the behaviour of the buyers. This topic is taken to know that which company has good position in the minds of buyer and to know the factors which the buyers consider at the time of purchase for two wheelers. The research will be helpful for the both companies because by this study as it be can know what are their strengths and where they are lacking.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out the model preferred among the selected brand.
- To understand the factors influencing the selected two wheelers.
- To make a comparative study of the selected brand and demographic factors.
- To know the market share of Honda and Bajaj.
- To determine the factors influencing the choice of buyer regarding two wheelers.

SOURCES OF DATA

1. Primary data
2. Secondary data

In this study both primary as well as secondary data have been used. The Secondary data means already existing or already published data collected and presented by somebody else or any organization or Government. The secondary data have been collected through books, Journals, Magazines, News Papers, Websites and other already published data.

Sample Design: sample size is 50. Random sample methods are followed. Out of 50, 26 respondents are users of Honda two wheelers and 24 respondents are users of Bajaj two wheelers.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The following tools and techniques have been used to present the data simple and clear. In this study statistical tool, simple percentage method Garrett Ranking Technique has been applied.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- ❖ The study is conducted only in Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli District.
- ❖ The duration of the study is limited.
- ❖ We have made analysis only 50 limited samples.
- ❖ Our study aims at buyers' preference for Honda and Bajaj two wheelers a comparative study.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Table 1.1. Occupation Wise Classification of Respondents

Sl. No.	PARTICULARS	HONDA		BAJAJ	
		No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Business	3	11.5	-	-
2	Government/Private employee	4	15.4	7	29.2
3	Students	15	57.7	13	54.2
4	Professional	2	7.7	2	8.3
5	Others	2	7.7	2	8.3
	Total	26	100	24	100

Source: Primary Data

Honda

The above table shows that out of 50 respondents, 11.5 percent of the respondents are business man, 15.4 percent of the respondents are government/ private employee, 57.7 percent of the respondents are students, 7.7 percent of the respondents are Professional employee, and 7.7 percent of the respondents are others. So it is concluded that most of the students are give importance to this Honda two wheelers.

Bajaj

The above table shows that out of 50 respondents, 29.2 percent of the respondents are government/ private employee, 54.2 percent of the respondents are students, 8.3 percent of the respondents are Professional employee, and 8.3 percent of the respondents are others. So it is concluded that most of the students are give importance to this Bajaj two wheelers.

TABLE 1.2. BIKE COLOR

Sl. No.	BIKE COLOR	HONDA		BAJAJ	
		No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Black	15	57.7	16	61.5
2	Blue	3	11.5	2	7.8
3	Red	3	11.5	4	15.4
4	Silver	4	15.4	1	3.8
5	Others	1	3.8	1	3.8
	Total	26	100	24	100

Source: Primary Data

Honda

The above table shows that out of 50 respondents, 57.7 percent of the respondents are prefer black color Honda two wheelers, 11.5 percent of the respondents are prefer blue color Honda two wheelers, 11.5 percent of the respondents are prefer red color Honda two wheelers, 15.4 percent of the respondents are prefer silver color Honda two wheelers, and 3.8 percent of the respondents are prefer other colors of Honda two wheelers. Therefore 57.7 percent of the respondents are preferred Black color of Honda two wheelers.

Bajaj

The above table shows that out of 50 respondents, 61.5 percent of the respondents are prefer black color Bajaj two wheelers, 7.8 percent of the respondents are prefer blue color Bajaj two wheelers, 15.4 percent of the respondents are prefer red color Bajaj two wheelers, 3.8 percent of the respondents are prefer silver color Bajaj two wheelers, and 3.8 percent of the respondents are prefer other colors of Bajaj two wheelers. Therefore 61.5 percent of the respondents are preferred black color of Bajaj two wheelers.

TABLE 1.3. MODELS OF HONDA TWO WHEELERS

Sl. No.	MODELS	HONDA	
		No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Honda Dio	10	38.6
2	Shine	6	23.1
3	unicorn	7	26.9
4	Activa	2	7.7
5	Others	1	3.8
	Total	26	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that out of 26 respondents, 38.6 percent of the respondents are using Honda Dio model two wheelers, 23.1 percent of the respondents are using Honda shine model two wheelers, 26.9 percent of the respondents are using Honda unicorn model two wheelers, 7.7 percent respondents are using Honda Activa model two wheelers, and 3.8 percent of the respondents are using other Models of Honda two wheelers. Therefore 38.6 percent of the respondents are using Honda Dio model two wheelers.

TABLE 1.4. MODELS OF BAJAJ TWO WHEELERS

Sl. No.	MODELS	BAJAJ	
		No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Pulsar	9	37.5
2	Platina	10	41.7
3	Bajaj CT110	2	8.3
4	Discover	2	8.3
5	Others	1	4.2
	Total	24	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that out of 24 respondents, 37.5 percent of the respondents are using Bajaj pulsar model two wheelers, 41.7 percent of the respondents are using Bajaj platina model two wheelers, 8.3 percent of the respondents are using Bajaj CT model two wheelers, 8.3 percent respondents are using Bajaj Discover model two wheelers, and 4.2 percent of the respondents are using others Bajaj Model two wheelers. Therefore 41.7 percent of the respondents are using Bajaj Platina model two wheelers.

TABLE 1.5 REASON FOR CHOOSING TWO WHEELERS

SL. NO.	REASON FOR CHOOSING	WEIGHTED MEANS	RANK
1	Brand	4.23	1
2	Colour	4.15	3
3	Mileage	3.84	4
4	Quality	3.69	6
5	Price	3.30	8
6	Model	3.73	5
7	Disk brake	2.96	9
8	Resale value	2.53	10
9	Speed	4.15	2
10	Smooth running	3.34	7

TABLE 1.6 LEVEL OF SATISFACTION FOR THE VEHICLE OBSERVED DATA

Sl. No.	Factors	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	No opinion	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied	Total
1	Image of the company	28	30	12	8	22	100
2	Model	38	34	10	8	10	100
3	Price	38	40	16	6	-	100
4	Mileage	10	54	22	8	6	100
5	Dealer value	16	40	24	16	4	100
6	Credit facility	8	18	40	24	10	100
7	Resale value	8	46	26	12	8	100
8	Smoothness riding	14	10	40	26	10	100
9	Safety	10	26	42	16	6	100
10	Carrying luggage	14	24	30	20	12	100

Source: Primary Data

While applying liker type scale to find out the level of satisfaction, the following weights are allotted.

- Highly Satisfied - 5
- Satisfied - 4
- No Opinion - 3
- Dissatisfied - 2
- Highly Satisfied - 1

Weighted Mean = Total/ No of Respondents

Finding

- It was Find out that Most of the respondents are Male.
- Most of the students are using Honda and Bajaj two wheelers.
- Most of the respondents are using black color Honda and Bajaj two wheelers.

- Majority of the respondents are choosing Honda Dio model two wheelers.
- Majority of the respondents are choosing Bajaj Platina model two wheelers.

Suggestion

- Brand image is the main factor influencing the purchase of two wheelers.
- Most of the respondents are feel that price is high. So two wheeler industry should taken effective steps to reduce the price of the two wheelers for the buyers.
- Respondents feel that pollution free two wheeler should be predicted.
- Color of the two wheelers should be attractive as per buyers' expectation. So that the sale can be increased.
- More advertisement should be given so as to reach poor people.

CONCLUSION

The study relating to buyers preference towards two wheeler in palayamkottai, tirunelveli District has been carried out in full devotion of time and energy by the researcher from collecting to analyzing the information. Research comes to a conclusion that most of the respondents prefer Honda and Bajaj two wheelers in other brand and two wheelers is purchased mainly for the growth of status. The main factors influencing the purchase of two wheelers are comfortable of two wheelers. Model is another important factors considered. With regards two wheelers get the major market share. Respondents prefer it own two wheelers in there will not be any reaction if price is increased but most of the respondents feel price is high.

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Magazines

- India today
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